

recovered from its ore solution by the proposed solvent extraction technique.

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Electrochromatographic Analysis of d-Block Cations

R. K. UPADHYAY*, K. RATHORE and ANJALI

Department of Chemistry, N.R.E.C. College, Khurja-203 131

Manuscript received 29 September 1984, revised 7 May 1985, accepted 11 September 1985

CHROMATOGRAPHIC analysis of cations complexed with a variety of organic ligands¹⁻³ including ketoanils⁴⁻⁸ are well documented. Electrochromatographic analysis of mixtures of II, III and IV group transition basic radicals and their mixtures with Au^{III}, complexed with *p*-diethylaminoanil of thiopheneglyoxal (DEATG) unknown as yet, has been described in the present note.

Experimental

p-Diethylaminoanil of thiopheneglyoxal and its complexes were prepared and isolated by the reported method⁹. In the synthetic work B.D.H. laboratory grade chemicals were used.

One or two drops of test solutions of moderate concentrations were applied in the middle of the 3×35 cm Whatman No. 1 filter paper strips with the help of fine capillaries and paper strips were dried in air. Loaded strips were carefully hanged in vertical type of apparatus having electrolytic solvent in its electrode chambers. When the paper strips were saturated with the solvent a constant voltage was applied for 1.5 to 3.0 h and chromatograms were dried in air. Direction and distance of spots from the point of application were noted.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes have shown unidirectional motion towards cathode. Migration rates of complexes spotted individually and in mixtures (Table 1) have not differed appreciably. Perusal of Table 1 shows that the method of electrophoresis could be successfully used to achieve qualitative separations of transitional basic radicals of II, III and IV groups and various mixtures of Au^{III} with Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}, in diverse developing solvents. Chromatogram fragments were identified by their own colours, which being highly stable retained for a long time.

TABLE 1—QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF COMPLEX MIXTURES

Complex mixture	Developing solvent	Spot colour	Distance travelled
Hg(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂ , H ₂ O	AcOMe-AcOH	Pink gray	2.2
Cd(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂	(1 : 1, v/v)	Yellow gray	0.8
Cr(DEATG)Cl ₃ , 4H ₂ O	MeOH-H ₂ O	Brown	1.5
Fe(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂	(4 : 1, v/v)	Brown	2.5
Mn(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	AcOMe-AcOH	Gray	0.2
Co(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂	(1 : 1, v/v)	Gray	0.7
Ni(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂		Pink	2.4
Zn(DEATG)Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O		Yellow	1.3
Au(DEATG)Cl ₃ .H ₂ O	AcOH	Orange	0.6
Ni(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂		Pink	0.0
Fe(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂		Brown	1.1
Au(DEATG)Cl ₃ .H ₂ O	AcOMe-AcOH	Orange	0.0
Cd(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂	(1 : 1, v/v)	Yellow gray	0.8
Zn(DEATG)Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O		Yellow	1.3
Hg(DEATG)Cl ₃ .H ₂ O		Pink gray/Pink	2.2 (or 2.4)
(or Ni(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂)			
Au(DEATG)Cl ₃ .H ₂ O	Iso-BuOH satd.	Orange	0.0
Co(DEATG)Cl ₃	with 0.1 N HCl	Gray	0.8
Ni(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂		Pink	1.4
Au(DEATG)Cl ₃ .H ₂ O	MeOH-H ₂ O	Orange	0.0
Ni(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂	(4 : 1, v/v)	Pink	0.8
Cr(DEATG)Cl ₃ .4H ₂ O		Brown	1.5
Fe(DEATG) ₂ Cl ₂		Brown	2.5

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[1,3]Dioxolo[4,5-g]pyrimido[1,2-a][3,1]benzothiazin-6-one

H. K. GAKHAR*, PUNAM SACHDEV

and

SHASHI BHUSHAN GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University,
Chandigarh-160 014

Manuscript received 4 December 1984,
accepted 11 September 1985

THE syntheses of some 1,3-dioxolo[4,5-g]pyrimido[1,2-a][3,1]benzothiazines with different alkyl-substituted-amino groups at 6-position has already been reported¹ from this laboratory. A review of literature reveals that noteworthy results are obtained by making structural variations in a section of the molecule. With this aim in mind, the synthesis of 1,3,3-trimethyl-3*H*,6*H*-[1,3]dioxolo[4,5-g]pyrimido[1,2-a][3,1]benzothiazine with a keto group at 6-position (6) has been undertaken.

It has been achieved by the condensation of methyl-6-aminopiperonylate (1) with 2-methyl-2-isothiocyanopentan-4-one (2). Isothiocyanates as well as the ketones are known to react with amines but the former are more reactive compared to the latter. Thus first step would lead to the formation of thiourea derivative, methyl-6-[[[(1,1-dimethyl-3-oxobutyl)amino]thioxomethyl]amino]-1,3-benzodioxole-5-carboxylate (3) which could give rise to 4 or 5 or a mixture of both depending upon the mode of cyclisation. However, even by careful experiments, only one product could be isolated as evident by tlc which has been assigned structure methyl-6[3,4-dihydro-4,4,6-trimethyl-2-thioxo-1(2*H*)pyrimidinyl]-1,3-benzodioxole-5-carboxylate (4) on the basis of ir spectra which gave a characteristic band at 1235 cm⁻¹ due to C=S. The C=O of the conjugated ester and N-H bands appeared at 1700 and 3150 cm⁻¹, respectively. Pmr spectra of 4 in CDCl₃ showed three singlets of three proton intensity each at δ 1.40, 1.46 and 1.57; the first two assignable to protons of the gem dimethyl groups and the last one

to three allylic protons (H_βC-C=CH-). Besides, it exhibited two more singlets, one of two proton intensity and the other of three proton intensity at δ 6.16 and 3.90 which are attributed to two methylenedioxy protons (-OCH₂O-) and two proton of the ester (-CO-OCH₃), respectively. It also exhibited two singlets of one proton intensity each at 4.85 and 6.86, the former due to one vinylic proton (C=CH-) and the latter due to single proton attached to nitrogen (NH exchangeable with D₂O). Two aromatic protons C₄-H and C₇-H appeared as two sharp singlets at δ 7.53 and 6.80, respectively. Moreover, the compound was found to be soluble in 10% sodium hydroxide solution which further supported the structure 4.

This has further been confirmed by preparing the isomeric compound 5 by an unambiguous route involving the condensation of 1 with 2-mercapto-4,4,6-trimethyl-1*H*,4*H*-(1,3)thiazine (8). The compound 5 thus formed, besides other signals, gave a singlet of three proton intensity at δ 3.86 assignable to ester but differed from the compound prepared by the condensation of 1 and 2 in m.p. and R_f value, and did not give any ir band around 1235 cm⁻¹, thus lending further support to structure 4. Moreover 5 was insoluble in 10% sodium hydroxide solution, which further confirmed structural assignment (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

4 on treatment with sodium ethoxide gave 6. The pmr spectrum of 6 in CDCl₃ showed the absence of a three proton singlet at δ 3.90 due to ester (-CO-OCH₃) and a singlet at 6.86 due to N-H. The protons of two gem dimethyl groups were observed as singlets of three proton intensity each at δ 1.23 and 1.33. There allylic protons (CH_β-C=CH-) appeared as a singlet at δ 1.53 and the lone vinylic proton (-C=CH-) appeared as a broad singlet at δ 5.37. Besides, it also showed one more singlet (2*H*) at δ 6.13 due to two methyl-